

EDUCATIONAL VIEWS OF MODERN THINKERS ON THE FORMATION OF PATRIOTISM IN STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927779>

Annotation: This article describes the essence of the educational views of the Eastern thinkers, which play an important role in the formation of the sense of patriotism in young students. The views of Jadid thinkers Abdulla Avloni, Abdurauf Fitrat, Cholpan on education are analyzed.

Key words: Eastern Renaissance, maturity, perfection, spirituality, spiritual education, physical health, mental ability, national tradition, value, scientific heritage, patriotism, perfection, reflection, education

The scientific heritage of Eastern thinkers, the rich literary masterpieces left by them, collections of Hadiths, and views on national and universal human values promoted in them serve as important foundations for educating young students in the spirit of patriotism.

In this regard, it is important to systematically teach the works of our great grandfather Alisher Navoi next year by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Therefore, Alisher Navoi's words that it is necessary to create concise examples of works that today's youth can understand, and to develop various mobile applications and electronic programs, explain how important the works of our great grandfather are in the education of the youth [1].

Art, literature, and sports play an important role in supporting young people in every way, making them spiritually mature and physically healthy, instilling feelings of love for the motherland in their minds. After all, the mental and physical maturity of the youth is a guarantee of the maturity of the future generations of this nation. The views on education in the scientific heritage of Eastern thinkers are important.

Our great-grandfather Mahmudhoja Behbudi emphasizes the following points about the necessity of paying attention to national education: "All nations and peoples of the earth attach great importance to the elementary education of their children, the discipline and wisdom of schools in all aspects, and they raise their children in a perfect image in the national and religious spirit. This is because foreign nationalities have national and religious sentiments and keep religion and nation sacred in everything. And, when necessary, they are ready to

sacrifice their property and lives on this road” [2]. In fact, the sense of patriotism is inculcated in the youth through national education.

At this point, it can be considered necessary to recognize the role of the mother tongue and literature in embodying national education in the heart and mind of the young students. Both of them have an equal role in the development of individuals with high moral virtues in the society. In this regard, the outstanding representative of modern literature, Abdulhamid Suleiman ugli Cholpan: “A nation whose literature is not dead and does not strive for the development of its literature and does not cultivate writers will one day be deprived of feelings, thoughts, and ideas, and will gradually become a crisis” [3]. Therefore, in the formation and development of the feeling of patriotism in the minds and hearts of young people, the native language and literature, instilled with the spirit of respect for our national traditions and values, serve as an important tool.

The moral views of the Islamic religion, distinguished by the promotion of the ideas of enlightenment and high morality, are the most influential and the most powerful in the moral and moral education of the people, without which it is impossible to imagine society, nation, human spirituality. It should be said that every verse of the Quran, every narration of the Hadiths is aimed at illuminating the moral qualities of believers, revealing their unique and beautiful aspects, and educating in this spirit. In them, it is repeated and repeated that every person should be humanitarian, patriotic, just, enlightened, spiritual, possessing high morals, creative, caring for loved ones [4].

Abdurauf Fitrat, a modern enlightener from Bukhara and one of the first Uzbek professors, also acknowledges the role of Islam in personal enlightenment, maturity and moral maturity: “Islam is our religion, Islam is our honor, Islam is our happiness. Islam is the cause of our pride, Islam is the cause of our tranquility [5]”. Indeed, in religious enlightenment, special attention is paid to the issues of love for the motherland, devotion to the motherland, kindness to parents, care for the enlightened, raising children and loyalty to the family. The ideas of doing meritorious deeds, not betraying someone's rights, being honest, pious, conscientious, loving the country, kindness, correctness, truthfulness, honesty, integrity, helping widows and destitutes, calling for humility were put forward.

In conclusion, the issues of the formation of a well-rounded person, moral qualities, creativity, caring for loved ones, humanitarianism, patriotism - a person's deep respect for his neighborhood, family, honor, pride and honor of his descendants, the responsibility of one's conscience and duties, and the ideas

of spiritual and moral education put forward in the legacy of our ancestors in recent years are still relevant today.

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